

Supplementary Figure S1. The transcription activity of *Gzmg* promoter assay between $\Delta 4$ -pGzmg and ΔS -pGzmg in the mouse zygote stage embryos. (A) The ΔS -pGzmg plasmid was constructed by a STAT3 binding site deletion from $\Delta 4$ -pGzmg using the site-direct mutagenesis. (B) Quantitative data of the *Gzmg* promoter assay obtained by the dual fluorescence system. The graph shows the means \pm SD of at least four replicates for each group of embryos. The *P* value ($p = 0.0006$) indicates a significant difference as determined by Student's t-test ($P < 0.001$).